

DEVELOPMENT OF XYLAPP_{EU}_2.1.2 FOR THE HARMONIZATION OF MONITORING DATA PROCESS OF XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA FROM FIELD TO LABORATORY

IF. SANTORO¹, S. GUALANO¹, G. FAVIA¹, J. BLASCO², C. KALAITZIDIS³,
A.M.D'ONGHIA^{1*}

¹CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DES HAUTES ETUDES AGRONOMIQUES MEDITERRANEENNES – MEDITERRANEAN AGRONOMIC INSTITUTE OF BARI. ²CENTRO DE AGROINGENIERIA, INSTITUTO VALENCIANO DE INVESTIGACIONES AGRARIAS (IVIA). ³CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DES HAUTES ETUDES AGRONOMIQUES MÉDITERRANÉENNES – MEDITERRANEAN AGRONOMIC INSTITUTE OF CHANIA.

***Corresponding author: donghia@iamb.it**

An advanced version of the android application XylApp_1.2.4, developed for the official monitoring of *Xylella fastidiosa* in Apulia region - Italy, was re-designed for accurate onsite data acquisition and traceability from the field to the laboratory in 3 EU pilot areas (Cordoba, Spain; Crete, Greece; Apulia, Italy). For the analysis of the functions for the EU Application suggestions and inputs by researchers and phytosanitary services of the pilot areas were also considered. For the implementation of the previous version of XylApp_{EU}_2.1.1 the following aspects were taken into account: (i) analysis of the scenario in the specific Country; (ii) identification of the specific needs and resolution conditions in relation to the different users; (iii) definition of the featured applications, constraints, performance, interfaces and any other features to fulfil user's needs; (iv) active engagement of end-users for the finalization and validation of the App. The advanced Application XylApp_{EU}_2.1.2 was equipped with grids of different sizes (e.g. 100m x 100m, 1km x 1km) of the 3 pilot sites, based on the free formats available from the European Environment Agency (EEA). With regard to the hardware and other minor functions, different parameters (sensor configuration, connectivity and size of the display) were implemented for the most popular platforms (e.g. Google Android). The following specific features were also implemented: - transmission protocols for data sending through internet; - inclusion of grids visualization of the pilot sites for sample localization at EU level (ETRS89-LAEA Europe); development of a GIS model for management of EU cartographic data. A new graphic interface has been made, user's friendly, which guarantee a better function and integration of modules, beside guidelines or a better management by users. This version allows the acquisition, storage and transmission of data in different formats. A video-tutorial on XylApp_{EU}_2.1.2 was prepared for dissemination purposes.